

METHODS OF FINDING THE FEELINGS OF TOLERANCE IN CHILDREN DURING GAME ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS.

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Abstract: This article provides insights into the pedagogical mechanisms of developing children's feelings of tolerance during play, information about the role of play in preschool educational organizations and its strengthening.

Key words: game, intellectual, education, tolerance, society, complex, pedagogue, environment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'yin faoliyati jarayonida bolalarda tolerantlik tuyg'ularini tarkib toptirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari haqida tushunchalar, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yinning o'rni va uni mustahkamlash haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'yin, intellektual, tarbiya, tolerantlik, jamiyat, kompleks, pedagog, muhit.

Аннотация: В статье представлены педагогические механизмы развития у детей чувства толерантности в процессе игры, сведения о роли игры в дошкольных образовательных организациях и ее укреплении.

Ключевые слова: игра, интеллектуал, воспитание, толерантность, общество, комплекс, педагог, среда.

Predstavleniya o pedagogicheskikh mechanismx razvitiya tolerantnosti u detey v processe iry, svedeniya o role iry v doskolnyx obrazovatelnyx i ee krepleni. Vajno, chtoby stoali ne tolko pokaseteli, no i chelovek, ego sotsialnye i duhovnye interesy.

V nashey respublike sistema obrazovaniya vseгда nakhoditsya pod vnimaniem gosudarstva. During the transition period, complex organizational and legal

measures were implemented to create an effective system of preschool education, aimed at ensuring the formation of a healthy and universally developed generation.

Many goals of social education can be realized through the creation and educational process of a good environment for children. B chastnosti, privilech v obrazovatelnoe uchrezhdenie vsekh detey, nezavisimo ot ikh sotsialnogo iskhozhdeniya; obespechenie polnogo vovlecheniya detey iz maloobespechennykh semey, semey, poteryavshikh blizkikh, i drugikh lits v obrazovanie; uchityvayutsya fizicheskie i intellektualnye razlichiya detey, sozdaetsya sreda v doskolnom obrazovanii; obespechenie vsem detyam ravnnykh vozmozhnostey v obrazovatelnom protsesse i t.d.

Fakticheski tolerantnost sformirovalas v istorii chelovechestva kak kriteriy tolerantnost i uvajitel'nogo atnosheniya k drugim religiyam i narodam. Poskolku tolerantnost means an unprejudiced attitude to tradition, culture, attitude and ideology, and it recognizes diversity. But in fact, tolerance as a very broad concept fully manifests itself in the system of historical, spiritual and educational values developed in Central Asia. During its rich and long history, our nation has experienced many events, which in itself left a significant mark on its material, spiritual culture, socio-economic and spiritual life.

Tolerance and nationalism should be considered as such a phenomenon that they did not appear by themselves in a few years by moving from one place to another or by introducing them, it is a product of history. It is necessary to look for the roots of these events in the distant history of our nation.

Entering preschool is a huge turning point for every child. From this period, the child in the family is obliged to perform not only family relations, but also private tasks necessary for his personality. With this, his role in the family does not seem to decrease, but on the contrary, it increases. That is, the period of protecting his reputation not only among family members, but on the contrary, among society, with his personal actions begins. However, the child will not be able to understand this yet.

Even simple concepts leave a mark on everyone at different speeds and powers. This phenomenon is primarily related to a person's personality, abilities and age.

Tolerance, as a social phenomenon, is also manifested in mutual social dialogues and expressions of attitude towards state and community organizations. By the nature of the content, such relations consist of proposals and recommendations created by the people's concern to attract the attention of the leaders of the state and public organizations to an important issue, to give importance to the problem based on the demands of justice or speed, without a pressure approach to the issue. This form of the phenomenon of tolerance is in the form of an objection or recognition of the content of the processes of managing the development of social events, and the attitude of the omrn in this regard is distinguished by its logicalness, conciseness, and indicative nature of the solution of the problem.

The view of tolerance as a form of manifestation of opinions is closely related to the task of mass control of society. The way of mass control of changes in social life, according to its essence, consists of several appearances and forms. They can be conditionally classified as follows: a) tolerance expressed in the system of dialogues, mutual relations and meetings in the order of state offices and institutions; in particular, respect for colleagues and leaders - obedience, thoughtfulness; b) attitude to the opinions expressed about everyday life, usual events and events. To approach issues with patience, express one's opinion with concern; c) tolerance manifested in the family environment, in the circle of friends, in the circle of like-minded people. In particular, the manifestation of the characteristics of not putting one's own interests first, not beating the character of others to the ground; g) exchanges of ideas on social issues that occur during weddings and events. For example: manifestation of the characteristics of kindness, honesty, faith, sympathy, equality, prudence, loyalty. According to Abu Rayhan Beruni's point of view, the emergence of tolerance is inextricably linked with social relations, people's way of life, material needs, interests, interests, demands and goals. For example, blindness

among people arose due to the need of people to get rid of the needs of mutual association and external dangers together. Beruni also notes that tolerance has gained historical importance in ensuring the viability of peoples.

The famous philosopher of the East, Abu Nasr Farabi, writes about tolerance: "There are no natural or voluntary ties between some people, it is necessary for each person to harm the interests of the state for his own benefit, and one must be a stranger to another. , because even if they unite, they unite because of necessity and obligation, even if they reach a compromise, they think that they will only come to an agreement when one of them wins and the others lose. In this, they are forced to come to an agreement under the pressure of an external force. This belief is one of the animal beliefs characteristic of humanity"¹². It can be seen from these thoughts of Farabi that he emphasizes the need for people to live together not by force, but voluntarily, and then mutual conflicts will stop, and it is necessary to live in cooperation. Or again: " Some people think that the bonds of connection between people are based on the common behavior, nature, verb and language of these people. Each nation has its own characteristics.

The method was started in the early 20th century by the Italian physician Maria Montessori, who developed his theories through scientific experiments with his students; this method was used in public and private schools in many parts of the world.¹

This requires clarifying the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the development of social activity of students, the pedagogical model of the

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1. ¹ Bobokulova Nazokat Yusufovna "PROCESSES OF THE WORLDWIDE EXPANSION OF THE MONTESSORI METHOD" Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 . 193|200 6
 2. Abjalova Hilola Raxmat qizi "USING COOPERATIVE METHODS IN FORMING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS" Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 261|265 6

development of social activity, and the use of interactive and modern technologies in the formation of the content of classes outside the auditorium.²

It is important to ensure that the same upbringing of children continues in educational organizations. It is expedient to pay special attention to this during training in activity centers organized in pre-school educational organizations. After all, it is important for children to grow up well, and for their future relationships to be creative.

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